

Acoustical study of substituted hydroxy-1,3-propanedione in dioxane-water mixtures in different concentrations

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Abstract : Ultrasonic velocity and density measurements of 1-(2'-hydroxy-5'-bromophenyl)-3-(4'-chlorophenyl)-1,3-propanedione (HB4CP) in dioxane-water mixture have been carried out in the concentration range 1×10^{-2} – 4×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ and in different percentages of dioxane-water mixtures. The experimental data have been used to calculate various acoustical parameters such as adiabatic compressibility (β_s), apparent molal volume (ϕ_v), apparent molal compressibility ($\phi_{K(S)}$), intermolecular free length (L_f), specific acoustic impedance (Z_s) and relative association (R_A). The results have been interpreted in terms of solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions.

Keywords : Acoustical study, mixed solvents.

The study of molecular interactions in liquids provide valuable information regarding internal structure, molecular association, complex formation, internal pressure etc. Various techniques are there to study them such as NMR, microwave, ultraviolet and infrared spectroscopy, neutron and X-ray scattering and ultrasonic investigation. Ultrasonic investigation has been the subject of exhaustive research and it finds extensive application in characterising physico-chemical behaviour and solute-solvent interactions¹. Recently² apparent molal volume, adiabatic compressibility, intermolecular free length, specific acoustic impedance and relative association of substituted azoles in *N,N*-dimethylformamide in different concentrations and at different temperatures have been investigated. The present attempt is made to determine the densities and ultrasonic velocities of above ligand in 70% dioxane-water mixture at different concentrations and in different percentages of dioxane-water mixtures at fixed concentration of solute (1×10^{-2} M) for predicting the solution properties.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The solvents were purified by standard procedures. The solute was synthesized by standard methods³. Density measurements were made by bicapillary pycnometer. The accuracy in density measurements was found to be ± 0.001 g/ml. The velocity of ultrasonic wave was determined by

variable path single crystal interferometer (Mittal Enterprise, Model MX-3) of 1 MHz with accuracy of $\pm 0.03\%$. The temperature was maintained at 305 K with an accuracy of 0.1.

The apparent molal volume (ϕ_v) and apparent molal adiabatic compressibility ($\phi_{K(S)}$) have been determined respectively from density (d_s) and adiabatic compressibility (β_s) of solution by using eqs. (1) and (2) respectively,

$$\phi_v = \frac{M}{d_s} + \frac{[(d_o - d_s) \times 10^3]}{m \cdot d_o \cdot d_s} \quad (1)$$

where d_o and d_s represent densities of solvent and solution respectively, m is the molality of solution and M is molecular weight of the solute.

$$\phi_{K(S)} = \frac{[(\beta_s d_o - \beta_o d_s) \times 10^3]}{m \cdot d_s \cdot d_o} + \frac{\beta_s M}{d_s} \quad (2)$$

where β_o and β_s are adiabatic compressibilities of solvent and solution respectively and are calculated by,

$$\beta_o = \frac{1}{U_o^2 \cdot d_o}, \quad \beta_s = \frac{1}{U_s^2 \cdot d_s}$$

where U_o and U_s are ultrasonic velocities of solvent and solution respectively. The ultrasonic velocity (U) is given by $U = \lambda \times \text{frequency}$, where λ is wave length of ultrasonic wave.

Table 1

(a) Acoustic parameters of (HB4CP) in different percentage of dioxane-water mixtures

Dioxane (%)	Ultrasonic velocity (U_s) (m/s) $\times 10^3$	Density (d_s) (g/m^3) $\times 10^6$	Adiabatic compressibility (β_s) (bar^{-1}) $\times 10^{-10}$	Intermolecular free length (L_f) (\AA) $\times 10^2$	Apparent molal volume (ϕ_v) (m^3/mol) $\times 10^{-6}$	Apparent molal compressibility ($\phi_{K(S)}$) ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{bar}^{-1}$) $\times 10^{-10}$	Relative association (R_A)	Specific acoustic impedance (Z_s) ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) $\times 10^6$
100	1.3173	1.0246	56.238	4.7453	201.91	-20.6512	0.34018	1.3497
90	1.4237	1.0297	47.907	4.3809	175.36	-29.5690	0.32472	1.4659
80	1.4382	1.0331	46.796	4.3257	142.73	-10.5581	0.33089	1.4858
75	1.4766	1.0348	44.319	4.2131	129.59	-6.7835	0.33173	1.5279
70	1.4906	1.0356	43.454	4.1700	114.79	-13.8337	0.33025	1.5406
60	1.5572	1.0381	39.723	3.9883	77.16	-23.3399	0.32813	1.6165

Note

(b) Acoustic parameters of (HB4CP) at different concentrations of solute in 70% dioxane-water mixture

Concentrations of ligand (m) (mol/dm ³)	Ultrasonic velocity (U_s) (m/s) $\times 10^3$	Density (d_s) (g/m^3) $\times 10^6$	Adiabatic compressibility (β_s) (bar^{-1}) $\times 10^{-10}$	Intermolecular free length (L_f) (\AA) $\times 10^2$	Apparent molal volume (ϕ_v) (m^3/mol) $\times 10^{-6}$	Apparent molal compressibility ($\phi_{K(S)}$) ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{bar}^{-1}$) $\times 10^{-10}$	Relative association (R_A)	Specific acoustic impedance (Z_s) ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) $\times 10^6$
1×10^{-2}	1.4939	1.03477	4.3302	4.1653	260.30	-10.3827	0.32925	1.5458
2×10^{-2}	1.4993	1.03642	4.2922	4.1460	223.48	-6.6332	0.32858	1.5539
3×10^{-2}	1.5021	1.03808	4.2694	4.1315	210.71	-4.8994	0.32850	1.5592
4×10^{-2}	1.5059	1.04057	4.2377	4.1169	184.71	-4.3239	0.32846	1.5669

Specific acoustic impedance (Z_s), relative association (R_A) and intermolecular free length (L_f) are the functions of ultrasonic velocity are given by⁴ : $Z_s = U_s \cdot d_s$, $R_A = (d_s/d_o)(U_o/U_s)^{1/3}$, $L_f = K \times \sqrt{\beta_s}$, where K is Jacobson's constant.

Results and discussion

In the present investigation different acoustic parameters such as adiabatic compressibility (β_s), apparent molal volume (ϕ_v), apparent molal compressibility ($\phi_{K(S)}$), acoustic impedance (Z_s), relative association (R_A) and intermolecular free length (L_f) of the solutions in different dioxane-water mixtures and at different concentrations of solute are determined at 305 K and presented in Table 1.

It is observed from the Table that the values of β_s decrease with decrease in percentage of dioxane in different percentages of dioxane-water mixtures at fixed concentration of solute ($1 \times 10^{-2} M$) and with increase in concentrations in 70% dioxane-water mixture. The decrease of β_s with increase in concentration of solute may be due to aggregation of solvent molecules around the ions, supporting strong ion-solvent interaction⁵.

The negative values of $\phi_{K(S)}$ may be due to loss of compressibility of solute due to strong electrostrictive solvation of ions. The values of $\phi_{K(S)}$ increase with increase in concentration of solute indicating increase in solute-solvent interactions and decrease in electrostrictive solvation of ions. The positive value ϕ_v at all compositions and percentage of dioxane are showing that the interactions are insensitive to solvent. It is seen that intermolecular free length (L_f) increases with increase in percentage of dioxane indicating weak interaction between ion and solvent molecules. This also implies increase in number of free ions showing ionic dissociation but weak ion-ion interactions.

Relative association (R_A) decreases due to breaking up of solvent molecules on addition of electrolyte to it and increases due to solvation of ions that are

simultaneously present. The specific acoustic impedance (Z_s) values decrease with increase in percentage of dioxane. It also supports weak ion-solvent interactions and electrostrictive solvation of ions. Also the acoustic impedance increases with increase in concentration of solute.

The values of ϕ_v , R_A , L_f decrease with increase in concentration of solute. This may be due to decreasing intermolecular interactions with addition of solute forming aggregate of solvent.

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